

Knowledge and Practice of Personal Hygiene among Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Benue State, Nigeria.

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Abstract: In recent years, thousands of people have been displaced in Benue State due to conflict or natural disasters and have been forced to live in makeshift camps known as IDPs' camps where there is high exposure to infectious diseases including those that are related to poor personal hygiene. Most studies focusing on IDPs in Benue State were skewed towards their social, economic and security well-being with little or no consideration for hygiene practices of the IDPs. There is no baseline data or information on the current knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State to provide baseline data and information for hygiene intervention programmes in IDPs' camps. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design. A sample size of 422 was drawn from a population of 26,214 IDPs living in officially recognized camps in Benue State. A researcher-developed Questionnaire (KPPHQ) pre-tested with reliability coefficients of 0.89 and 0.92 for knowledge and practice sections, respectively, was used for data collection. Descriptive statistics were used to describe participants' characteristics and to analyse responses on personal hygiene knowledge and practice. Pearson chi-square was used to test for association between knowledge/practice of hygiene and the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants at $P < .05$. The results showed that majority of the participants (54.6%) demonstrated poor knowledge of personal hygiene. Majority (74.6%) also demonstrated poor practice of personal hygiene. Good knowledge of personal hygiene was observed to be significantly associated with being female ($\chi^2 = 41.04, p = .002$); being of younger age group ($\chi^2 = 58.98, p = .001$); being single ($\chi^2 = 33.38, p = .003$); and acquiring tertiary education ($\chi^2 = 60.45, p < .001$). Good practice of personal hygiene was also significantly associated with the female gender ($\chi^2 = 52.40, p < .001$); younger age group ($\chi^2 = 38.50, p = .004$); single marital status ($\chi^2 = 43.96, p = .004$); and acquiring tertiary education ($\chi^2 = 65.89, p < .001$). Introduction and reinforcement of targeted health education intervention in the IDPs' Camps with emphasis on hygiene and sanitation to improve IDPs' knowledge and practice of personal hygiene is hereby recommended.

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1.0 Introduction

Thousands of people are displaced globally every year due to wars and natural disasters. According to the report by Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC, 2022), the internal displacements in 2021 globally amounted to 53.2 million people by conflict and 5.9 million by natural disasters. In Nigeria, the activities of Boko Haram and other non-state armed groups have led to significant displacement in the country since 2009 (IDMC, 2022). In North-Central Nigeria, intercommunal clashes resulting from ethno-religious disputes between Fulani herdsmen militia and farmers have resulted in over one million people being displaced from their homes (Egbere et al., 2020). Similarly, a report by International Organisation for Migration (IOM, 2024) showed that Benue State has the highest IDPs concentration in

North-Central Nigeria (500,182 IDPs or 41 per cent of the total internally displaced persons (IDPs) population in the North-Central). IDPs are persons who are forced to flee their homes and take abode in makeshift camps and who have not crossed an internationally recognised State boundary.

A major fallout of this displacement is the creation of IDPs' camps across Nigeria including Benue State. In the camps, IDPs are often exposed to infectious diseases because of the temporary nature of their abode and inadequate hygiene facilities (Owoaje et al., 2016; Lam et al., 2015; Olwedo et al., 2008). In Benue State, these camps are mainly school facilities and empty government buildings with few or no basic amenities. Daodu et al. (2024) observed that overcrowding, lack of clean water and hygiene kits were the major humanitarian crisis in the IDPs' camps in Benue State. Several risk factors work in synergy to promote infection of diseases among IDPs. For instance, Ede (2018) observed that risk factors such as resettlement in temporary locations, overcrowding, environmental degradation, inadequacy of safe water, poor sanitation and waste management have escalated the prevalence of infectious diseases among IDPs in Benue State. The combined effects of these factors have increased the risk of exposure to acute respiratory infections, diarrhoea, gastrointestinal diseases, malaria, scabies, chicken pox and measles among IDPs in Benue State (Ede, 2018), which could be minimised by good personal hygiene knowledge and practices.

Personal hygiene typically refers to the practice of keeping oneself and one's surroundings clean especially to prevent illnesses or control diseases (Gebreyesus, & Adem 2018). Jung et al. (2016) observed that hygiene-related diseases and other infectious diseases account for 80% of mortality rate in developing countries. This is a clear indication that good hygiene practices are essential for optimal health and wellbeing. Knowledge of personal hygiene refers to the familiarity and understanding of the facts about hygiene practice. It encompasses the awareness of the need for personal hygiene and its basic principles. Poor knowledge of personal hygiene could lead to outbreak of diseases in IDPs' camps. This is because low priority for personal hygiene as a result of poor knowledge could prevent IDPs from responding to important prerequisites for a healthy living (Ali et al., 2021).

There is a dearth of literature on knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs. A study by Mubarak et al. (2016) found poor hygiene practices among IDPs in Kabul, Afghanistan. In Nigeria, a study by Ali et al. (2021) reported good knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Maiduguri, Borno State. In contrast, Egberé et al. (2020) found that the hand hygiene practice (a component of personal hygiene) score of the IDPs in Jos and environs, Plateau State was poor (34.0%). Studies have also reported significant association between knowledge/practice of personal hygiene and gender (Ghanim et al., 2016), age (Rajbhandari et al., 2018), marital status (Ali et al., 2021) and level of education (Fehintola et al., 2017).

In spite of the disadvantaged position of IDPs in Benue State, there is no baseline data or information on their current knowledge and practice of personal hygiene to the best of the researchers' knowledge. Most studies focusing on IDPs in Benue State were skewed towards their social, economic and security well-being with little or no consideration for hygiene practices among them (Inyang & Effiong, 2022; Ukase & Jato, 2022). Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State to provide baseline data and information for hygiene intervention programmes in the IDPs' camps.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Study Design

Mixed cross-sectional research design method was used. This approach deployed both quantitative and qualitative data collection from a sample of a population at a single point in time (Adhikary et al. 2022). It allows researchers to gain a deeper understanding of a phenomenon by exploring both numerical data and rich descriptive insights (Spector 2019, Adhikary et al. 2022). The mixed cross-sectional design was considered more appropriate than other designs for describing the knowledge and practice of hygiene among IDPs in Benue State to provide baseline data for intervention policies and strategies.

2.2 Case Study Area

Figure 1: Map showing the number of registered IDPs in six affected LGAs in Benue State

Map showing number of IDPs registered by LGA

(source: International Organisation for Migration, 2024).

This study was conducted in Benue State of Nigeria. Located in the North-Central Nigeria, Benue State occupies 34,059 square kilometres and lies between latitudes 6° 25" and 8° 25" N, and on longitudes 7° 47" and 10° 00" E in the Central part of Nigeria. The State shares boundaries with Nasarawa State in the North and Taraba State in the Northeast. In the South, it shares boundary with Cross River State, while its southwest boundary is shared with Enugu and Ebonyi States. To the West, it is bounded by Kogi State, while a short international boundary is shared with the Republic of Cameroon around Kwande Local Government Area (Hula, 2013). According to the National Population Commission (2006), Benue State has a population of four million, two hundred and fifty-three thousand, six hundred and forty-one (4,253,641) people as at the last census in 2006 and agriculture employs more than 70% of this population.

Benue State is located within the Guinea Savana belt which is also the broadest vegetation zone in Nigeria and is characterized by heterogeneous species of scattered trees and grasses (Hula, 2010). However, persistent clearance of the vegetation for arable agriculture, lumbering and the practice of bush fallowing system create regrowth and characteristic parklands that attract animal grazing and cattle herdsman. This has caused persistent farmers-herders crisis resulting in displacement of many persons and establishment of IDPs' camps in Benue State.

According to the International Organisation for Migration (IOM, 2024), Benue State has the highest IDPs concentration in North-Central Nigeria (500,182 IDPs or 41 per cent of the total IDPs population in the North-Central). This figure includes IDPs in both official and non-official camps. The report by the IOM (2024) further showed that there were 34 IDP' camps located in six LGAs in Benue State: Agatu (3 camps), Guma (8 camps), Gwer-west (4 camps), Kwande (1 camp), Logo (2 camps) and Makurdi (16 camps). Six of these camps are officially recognized by the Government while 28 are not yet officially recognized. The officially recognized IDPs' camps include Gbajimba camp, Daudu camp 1, Daudu camp 2, Daudu camp 3, Abagena camp, and LGEA Primary School Agan camp. The unofficial camps were self-created by IDP in Makurdi, Agatu, Guma, Gwer-West, Kwande, Okpokwu and Logo Local Government Areas. Ede (2018) observed that IDP camps in Benue State are overcrowded and characterized by environmental degradation, inadequacy of safe water, poor sanitation and hygiene, which have promoted the spread of infectious diseases on IDP camps. The effects of these factors could be minimized if IDPs possess correct knowledge and imbibe

good personal hygiene practices. This study, therefore, assessed the knowledge and practice of hygiene among IDPs in Benue State.

Figure 2: Gbajimba IDPs' Camp, Duru, 2024

Figure 3: Abagena IDPs Camp, Obande, 2024

Figure 4: Agan IDPs Camp, Benue State, Otakom, 2021

2.3 Study Population

The population comprised all duly registered IDPs in Benue State. According to the IOM (2024), there were 160,631 duly registered IDPs in Benue State as at July, 2024.

2.4 Sampling Method

Five out of the six officially recognized IDP camps were purposively selected for this study. Three camps (Gbajimba, Daudu I and Daudu II) from Guma LGA and two camps (Abagena and LGEA Primary School, Agan) from Makurdi LGA. These camps were selected because of their dense concentration of IDP population. A sample size of 422 was arrived at using the Kish and Leslie sampling formula for cross-sectional studies.

$$N = \frac{p(1-p)z^2}{d^2}$$

Where:

N = Sample size

p = Estimated proportion

d = Estimated margin of error and

z = standard normal deviation at 95% confidence interval

The following assumptions were made:

- (1) p = 0.5 (assuming that knowledge and practice of hygiene among IDPs in Benue State were average).
- (2) z = 1.96 (corresponding with 95% confidence interval,) and
- (3) d = 0.05 (which is the margin of error)

$$N = \frac{0.5(1 - 0.5)(1.96)^2}{(0.05)^2} = 384$$

Adding an attrition rate of 10% i.e $10 \times \frac{384}{100} = 38.4$

Therefore, the sample size was $384 + 38 = 422$

Purposive sampling procedure was adopted to select 422 respondents from the selected five IDPs' camps.

2.5 Description of Data Collection Tool

A researcher-developed tool entitled “knowledge and practice of personal hygiene questionnaire (KPPHQ)” was used for data collection. The questionnaire comprised three sections with a total number of 26 items. Section A which sought information on the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents has 4 items on age, gender, marital status and level of education. Section B contained assessment questions on knowledge of personal hygiene (13 items) and Section C contained assessment questions on practice of personal hygiene (9 items). The KAP model guided the development of this questionnaire. For the knowledge items, the response options were “True or False or Not sure”. The 'not sure' option was included to avoid guessing (Matošková, 2016). For scoring the knowledge items, any correct answer gets a score of '1' while any wrong or not sure answer gets a score of '0'. For the practice items, the response options were Never (1), Rarely (2), Often (3), and Very Often (4). Negative items were reverse scored, so that a higher score indicates good practice while a lower score indicates poor practice of hygiene.

KPPHQ was presented to three experts in Health Education, one expert in Science Education and one in Test and Measurement all of Benue State University, Makurdi for checking the adequacy of the items and their appropriateness in measuring what they were supposed to measure. The inputs of the experts were used in the final construction of the instrument. Thereafter, KPPHQ was subjected to a reliability test using 20 IDPs from Ichwa and Ogiri Ajene camps which are un-official IDP camps in Benue State. Cronbach's alpha was used to compute internal consistency of the questionnaire. The results show a reliability coefficient of 0.89 and 0.92 for the knowledge and practice sections of the questionnaire, respectively. These reliability coefficients were more than the cut-off (0.70) recommended by Taber (2018) indicating good internal consistency for the newly developed KPPHQ.

2.6 Data Analysis

Data were analysed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), Version 26. Frequencies and percentages were used to describe the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants and to determine the level of knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs. Knowledge was categorized into three: good (70% and above), average (50% to 69%) and poor (below 50%) (Rajbhandari et al., 2018). Practice was categorized into three: good (70% and above), moderate (50 to 69%) and poor (below 50%). Pearson chi-square was used to test for association between knowledge/practice and the sociodemographic characteristics. Significant associations were declared at $P < .05$.

3.0 Results

3.1 Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. The sample size was 422 out of which 410 participants successfully completed the questionnaires. Majority 294 (71.7%) of the participants were males, 215 (52.4%) were within the age range of 30-39 years. Most of the participants, 296 (72.4%) were married, while 242 (59.0%) had completed only primary education.

Table 1:

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants (n=410)

Sociodemographic variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	294	71.7
Female	116	28.3
Age range(in Years)		
20-29	60	14.6
30-39	215	52.4
40-49	100	24.4
50 and above	35	8.6
Marital status		
Single	36	8.8
Married	297	72.4
Widowed	59	14.4
Separated	18	4.4
Level of Education		
No formal education	80	19.5
Primary	242	59.0
Secondary	68	16.6
Tertiary	20	4.9

3.2 Participants' Knowledge of Personal Hygiene

Table 2 presents the analysis on knowledge of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State. The result shows that majority (69.5%) of the respondents understand that personal hygiene involves maintaining the cleanliness of the body, majority (53.4%) knew that daily bathing with soap prevents diseases. More than half (52.4%) knew that dandruff could be caused by not washing the hair regularly, and majority (53.75) knew that using teeth to cut fingernails is harmful.

The questions with the lowest correct responses were question 4: irregular bathing can cause scabies (35.1%); question 6: washing hands with water and soap after visiting toilet is not necessary (38.3%); question 9: walking barefoot can cause hookworm infection (36.8%); question 10: using sticks for anal cleaning after defecation is harmful (37.3%); and question 11: it is important to change used clothes for clean ones everyday (37.3%). The overall personal hygiene correct response score was 45.1% (below 50%) indicating poor knowledge of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State.

Table 2:*Frequency and Percentage Analysis on Knowledge of Personal Hygiene among IDPs in Benue State (n = 410)*

S/N	Statement	Correct	Wrong
		n (%)	n (%)
1	Personal hygiene involves maintaining the cleanliness of the body.	286 (69.5)	125 (30.5)
2	Daily bathing with soap prevents diseases	219 (53.4)	191 (46.6)
3	Regular cleaning of the genitals prevents infections	169 (41.2)	241 (58.8)
4	Irregular bathing can cause scabies	144 (35.1)	266 (64.9)
5	Brushing teeth regularly prevents teeth problems	202 (49.3)	208 (50.7)
6	Washing hands with water and soap after visiting the toilet is not necessary.	157 (38.3)	253 (61.7)
7	It is dangerous not to wash hands with water and soap after handling pets or domestic animals.	169 (41.2)	241 (58.8)
8	Dandruff could be caused by not washing hair regularly	215 (52.4)	195 (47.6)
9	Walking barefooted can cause hookworm infection	151 (36.8)	259 (63.2)
10	Using sticks for anal cleaning after defecation is harmful	153 (37.3)	257 (62.7)
11	It is important to change used clothes for clean ones everyday	153 (37.3)	257 (62.7)
12	Using rags in place of sanitary pads during menstruation is harmful.	168 (41.0)	242 (59.0)
13	Using teeth to cut fingernails is harmful	220 (53.7)	190 (46.3)
Overall Knowledge Score		185 (45.1)	225 (54.9)

Figure 2 presents the categorization of IDPs' knowledge of personal hygiene. It shows that IDPs' poor knowledge of personal hygiene had the highest percentage score (54.6%), followed by good knowledge (25.4%) and average knowledge with the lowest percentage score (20.0%). This indicates that IDPs in Benue State had poor knowledge of personal hygiene.

Figure 2: Categorization of IDPs' Knowledge of Personal Hygiene

3.3 Participants' Practice of Personal Hygiene

Table 3 presents frequency and percentage analysis on personal hygiene practices among IDPs in Benue State. The Table indicates that about 157 (38.3%) participants rarely took their bath with soap; about 291 (71.0%) never washed their hands with soap after visiting toilet; more than half of the participants (52.7%) indicated never brushing their teeth with fluoride toothpaste, 38.3% of the participants rarely washed their genital areas with clean water; while 71.0% of the participants indicated never washing their hands with soap and water after handling pets or domestic animals. When asked how often they change used clothes for clean ones everyday, more than half (52.7%) of the participants indicated never doing it. A good number of the participants (38.3%), however, indicated that they often put on their foot wears.

On how often they use tissue paper for anal cleaning after defecation, 38.3% of the participants indicated never doing it; majority of the participants (88.5%) indicated never sterilizing instruments for cutting fingernails. The result further shows overall personal hygiene practice scores of 11.7% and 20.0% for “very often” and “often”, respectively (which are below 50%), indicating poor practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State.

Table 3:

Frequency and Percentage Analysis on Practice of Personal Hygiene among IDPs in Benue State, Nigeria. n= (410)

N	Question	Very often	Often	Rarely	Never
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
	How often do you bath with soap?	122 (29.8)	131 (32.0)	157 (38.3)	0 (0.0)
	How often do you wash your hands with soap after using toilet?	8 (2.0)	39 (9.5)	72 (17.6)	291 (71.0)
	How often do you brush your teeth with fluoride toothpaste?	26 (6.3)	53 (12.9)	115 (28.0)	216 (52.7)
	How often do you wash your genital areas with clean water?	122 (29.8)	131 (32.0)	157 (38.3)	0 (0.0)
	How often do you wash your hands with soap after handling pets or domestic animals?	8 (2.0)	39 (9.5)	72 (17.6)	291 (71.0)
	How often do you change used clothes for clean ones every day?	26 (6.3)	53 (12.9)	115 (28.0)	216 (52.7)
	How often do you put on your foot wears?	122 (29.8)	157 (38.3)	131 (32.0)	0 (0.0)
	How often do you use tissue paper for anal cleaning after defecation?	0 (0.0)	122 (29.8)	131 (32.0)	157 (38.3)
	How often do you use sterilized instrument to cut your fingernails?	0 (0.0)	15 (3.7)	32 (7.8)	368 (88.5)
	Overall Practice Score	48 (11.7)	82 (20.0)	109 (26.6)	171 (41.7)

Figure 3 presents categorization of personal hygiene practice among IDPs in Benue State. It shows that a few IDPs 8 (2.0%) demonstrated good practice of personal hygiene (scored 70% and above), 23.4% demonstrated moderate practice of personal hygiene (scored 50 – 69%), and majority (74.6%) demonstrated poor practice of personal hygiene (scored above 50%). This indicates poor practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State.

Figure 3: Categorization of IDPs' Practice of Personal Hygiene

3.4 Association between Knowledge of Personal Hygiene and the Sociodemographic Characteristics

Table 4 presents chi-square analysis on the association between knowledge of personal hygiene and the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. The result indicates significant association between knowledge of personal hygiene and gender, $\chi^2(2, N = 410) = 41.04, p = .002$ with the female participants having better knowledge of personal hygiene than the males. There was also a significant association between knowledge of personal hygiene and age, $\chi^2(6, N = 410) = 58.98, p = .001$ with participants of younger age (20 – 29yrs) demonstrating better knowledge of personal hygiene than those in the older age categories. A significant association was also observed between knowledge of personal hygiene and marital status, $\chi^2(6, N = 410) = 33.38, p = .003$ with the respondents of single status demonstrating better knowledge of personal hygiene than those that were married, separated and divorced. The result also indicates a significant association between knowledge of personal hygiene and level of education, $\chi^2(6, N = 410) = 60.45, p < .001$ with participants with tertiary education demonstrating better knowledge of personal hygiene than those with lower level of education.

Table 4:

Chi-square (χ^2) Analysis on Differences in the Knowledge of Personal Hygiene among IDPs based on Gender, Age, Marital Status and Level of Education (n = 410)

Variable	N	Knowledge of Personal Hygiene			Df	χ^2	p-value
		Good f(%)	Average f(%)	Poor f(%)			
Gender							
Male	294	78 (26.5)	56 (19.1)	160 (54.4)	2	41.04	.002*
Female	116	46 (39.7)	26 (22.4)	44 (37.9)			
Age (in Years)							
20 – 29	60	29 (48.3)	25 (41.7)	6 (10.0)	6	58.98	.001*
30 – 39	215	55 (25.6)	51 (23.7)	109 (50.7)			
40 – 49	100	24 (24.0)	22 (22.0)	54 (54.0)			
50 & above	35	7 (20.0)	8 (22.9)	20 (57.1)			
Marital Status							
Single	36	15 (41.7)	12 (33.3)	9 (25.0)	6	33.38	.003*
Married	297	90 (30.3)	98 (33.0)	109 (36.7)			
Widowed	59	14 (23.7)	17 (28.8)	28 (47.5)			
Separated	18	5 (27.8)	4 (22.2)	9 (50.0)			
Level of Education							
No formal education	80	8 (10.0)	14 (17.5)	58 (72.5)	6	60.45	< .001*
Primary	242	54 (22.3)	44 (18.2)	144 (59.5)			
Secondary	68	27 (39.7)	22 (32.4)	19 (27.9)			
Tertiary	20	15 (75.0)	3 (15.0)	2 (10.0)			

* significant at $p < .05$

3.5 Association between Practice of Personal Hygiene and the Sociodemographic Characteristics

Table 5 presents chi-square analysis on association between practice of personal hygiene and the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. The result indicates a significant association between practice of personal hygiene and gender difference, $\chi^2(2, n=410) = 52.40, p < .001$, with the females dominating the good practice of personal hygiene. Significant association was also observed between practice of personal hygiene and age, $\chi^2(6, n = 410) = 38.50, p = .004$, with the younger participants demonstrating better practice of personal hygiene than the older participants. On marital status too, a significant association existed, $\chi^2(6, n = 410) = 43.96, P = .002$. Participants who were single had better

practice of personal hygiene as compared to other categories. The result also indicates a significant association between practice of personal hygiene and level of education, $\chi^2(6, n = 410) = 65.89, P < .001$, with participants who attended tertiary education demonstrating better practice of personal hygiene than those with lower educational attainment.

Table 5:

Chi-square Analysis on the Association between Practice of Personal Hygiene and the Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 410)

Variable	N	Practice of Personal Hygiene			Df	χ^2	p-value
		Good f (%)	Moderate f (%)	Poor f (%)			
Gender							
Male	294	4 (1.4)	72 (24.5)	218 (74.1)	2	52.40	<.001*
Female	116	24 (20.7)	30 (25.9)	62 (53.4)			
Age (in Years)							
20 – 29	60	15 (25.0)	35 (58.3)	10 (16.7)	6	38.50	.004*
30 – 39	215	43 (20.0)	10 (4.7)	162 (75.3)			
40 – 49	100	4 (4.0)	23 (23.0)	73 (73.0)			
50 & above	35	0 (0.0)	8 (22.9)	27 (77.1)			
Marital Status							
Single	36	15 (41.7)	12 (33.3)	9 (25.0)	6	43.96	.002*
Married	297	98 (33.0)	90 (30.3)	109 (36.7)			
Widowed	59	15 (25.4)	17 (28.8)	27 (45.8)			
Separated	18	5 (27.8)	4 (22.2)	9 (50.0)			
Level of Education							
No formal education	80	9 (11.3)	14 (17.5)	57 (71.3)	6	65.89	<.001*
Primary	242	54 (22.3)	44 (18.2)	144 (59.5)			
Secondary	68	22 (32.4)	27 (39.7)	19 (27.9)			
Tertiary	20	14 (70.0)	4 (20.0)	2 (10.0)			

* significant at $p < .05$

4.0 Discussion and Conclusion

This study assessed knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State, Nigeria. The study also tested for association between knowledge/practice of personal hygiene and sociodemographic characteristics (gender, age, marital status and level of education) of the participants. The result showed that more than half (54.6%) of the participants demonstrated poor knowledge of personal hygiene (Figure 2). This finding contrasts that of Ali et al. (2021) which reported that majority (70%) of IDPs in Maiduguri, Borno State had good knowledge of personal hygiene. This difference could be explained by the fact that the IDPs that participated in the study in Borno State had just attended a programme on awareness of personal hygiene, which may have influenced their good knowledge of the subject matter. This underscores the importance of awareness and sensitization programmes on personal hygiene in IDP camps. This finding is undesirable because the high prevalence of acute respiratory infections, diarrhea, scabies, chicken pox and measles among IDPs in Benue State as reported by Ede (2018) could partly be explained by the IDPs' poor knowledge of personal hygiene. Ali et al. (2021) observed that poor knowledge of personal hygiene could prevent IDPs from responding to important prerequisites for a healthy living leading to outbreak of diseases in IDPs' camps. We propose for a health education intervention research on personal hygiene among IDPs to curtail the rising prevalence of personal hygiene-related diseases in the IDPs' camps.

The result of this study also revealed that 74.6% of the participants demonstrated poor practice of personal hygiene (Figure 3). This finding is in agreement with Egberet al. (2020) who found that the hand hygiene practice (a component

of personal hygiene) score of the IDPs in Jos and environs, Plateau State was poor (34.0%). Similar finding was reported by Mubarak et al. (2016) among IDPs in Kabul, Afghanistan. The finding could be attributed to the poor personal hygiene knowledge of the IDPs as earlier reported in this study. The finding may also be attributed to the lack of some necessary hygiene kits and materials at the disposal of IDPs in Benue State as observed by Daodu et al. (2024). The poor practice of personal hygiene among IDPs in Benue State may have contributed to the worrisome prevalence of acute respiratory infections, diarrhoea, gastrointestinal diseases, scabies, chicken pox and measles as observed by Ede (2018). This finding calls for intensive hygiene education on IDPs' camps and provision of personal hygiene kits by the government and humanitarian organisations to improve personal hygiene practices of the IDPs.

This study further revealed that good knowledge and practice of personal hygiene were significantly associated with being female, being younger in age, being single and acquiring tertiary education (Tables 4 and 5). The finding on the association between knowledge/practice of personal hygiene and gender agrees with Ghanim et al. (2016) who reported higher knowledge and practice scores on personal hygiene among girls as compared to boys. This could be as a result of the female gender naturally being more conscious of their body and its cleanliness than their male counterparts. On age, the finding disagrees with Rajbhandari et al. (2018) who reported better knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among older students (15 – 16yrs) than younger students (below 15yrs). It could be that the participants in the present study comprised of adults too who may have not been students in their lives. The finding showing better knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among respondents who were single than those of other marital status aligns with Ali et al. (2021) who reported similar finding. The possible explanation could be that those who are single may still be in school where they may have acquired knowledge on personal hygiene and other health-related issues. The finding indicating better knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among respondents with tertiary education than those with lower level of education is consistent with the finding of a previous study (Fehintola et al., 2017). A possible explanation could be that those who have attained higher education have more exposure to educational materials on personal hygiene. The finding indicates that the higher one goes in knowledge acquisition in a formal school setting, the higher the knowledge and practice of personal hygiene.

In conclusion, the findings for this study call for urgent introduction and reinforcement of health education interventions in the IDP Camps with emphasis on hygiene and sanitation to improve IDPs' knowledge and practice of personal hygiene for better health and wellbeing. The findings on the differences in the knowledge and practice of personal among IDPs on account of gender, age, marital status and level of education underscore the necessity for targeted interventions focusing on males, older persons, the married and those with no or low level of education.

References

- Adhikary P, Roy N, Mburu G, Kabra R, Habib NA, et al. (2022) Characteristics, experiences and actions taken by women to address delayed conception: A mixed-methods cross-sectional study protocol. *PLOS ONE* 17(3): e0264777. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264777>
- Ali, B. I., Okwute, A., & Ojo, T. (2021). Assessment of the level of awareness and practice of personal hygiene among internally displaced persons in Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 9(3), 107-112
- Daodu, F.F., Shabu, T., Kile, T.V. & Enefu, J. (2024). Humanitarian crisis in internally displaced persons (IDPs) camps in Benue State: a comprehensive analysis. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, 8 (5), 2282-2298. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2024.805166>
- Duru, P. (2024, September 17). Benue's humanitarian crises worsens as IDPs camps swell to over 1.8M. *Vanguard Newspaper*: <https://libraryguides.vu.edu.au/apa-referencing/7Newspapers>

- Ede, V. I. (2018). Addressing the plights of the internally displaced persons in Nigeria: a Christian response. *Journal of Advanced Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 5(4), 1-9.
- Egbere, J. O., Odu, C. E., Ngene, A. C., Danladi, M. M. A., Ohaegbu, C. G., & Ayika P. D. (2020). Assessment of the hand hygiene status of internally displaced persons in Jos and environs, Nigeria. *African Journal of Microbiology Research* 14(11), 608-616.
- Fehintola, F. O., Fehintola, A. O., Aremu, A. O., Idowu, A., Ogunlaja, O. A., & Ogunlaja, I. P. (2017). Assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice about menstruation and menstrual hygiene among secondary high school girls in Ogbomoso, Oyo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 6(5), 1726-1732.
- Gebreeyessus, G. D., & Adem, D. B. (2018) Knowledge, attitude and practice of hygiene and morbidity status among tertiary students: the case of Kotebo Metropolitan University, Addis Ababa. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2018, 2094621. Doi:10.1155/2018/2094621.
- Ghanim M., Dash, N., Abdullah, B., Issa, H., Albarazi, R. & Al Salehi, Z. (2016) Knowledge and practice of Personal hygiene among primary school children in Sharjah-UAE. *Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(5), 67-73.
- Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (2022). Global report on internal displacements, Retrieved from <https://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2022/>
- International Organisation for Migration (IOM, 2024). Biometric registration progress report. https://dtm.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11461/files/reports/Biometric%20Registration%20Report%20Benue%20State_01%20July%202024_V3.pdf
- Inyang, E. B., & Effiong, E. N. (2022). Humanitarian intervention in Nigeria: A case of internally displaced People in Benue State, 2018–2021. Available at SSRN 3998209.
- Jung, S., Doh, Y., Bizuneh, D., Beyene, H., Seong, J., Kwon, H. & Cha, S. (2016) The effects of improved sanitation on Diarrheal prevalence, incidence and duration in children under five in the SNNPR State, Ethiopia: study protocol for randomized controlled trial, 17(1), 1-10
- Lam, E., McCarthy, A., & Brennan, M. (2015). Vaccine-preventable diseases in humanitarian emergencies among refugee and internally displaced populations. *Humanitarian vaccine and Immunotherapeutics*, 11(11) 2627-2636
- Mubarak, M. Y., Wagner, A.L., Asami, M., Carlson, B. F., & Boulton, M.L. (2016). Hygienic practices and diarrheal illness among persons living in at-risk settings in Kabul, Afghanistan: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Infectious diseases*, 16(1), 1-9
- Obande, S. (2024, December 2). Why IDPs in Benue cannot go home. *Displacement & Migration News*. <https://humanglemedia.com/why-idps-in-benue-cannot-go-home/>
- Olwedo, M. A., Mworozzi, E., Bachou, H., & Orach, C. G. (2008). Factors associated with malnutrition among children in internally displaced person's camps, northern Uganda. *African Health Sciences Journal*, 8(4), 244-252.
- Otakom, A. (2021, May 6). Inside Benue IDPs' camp where mosquito net 'cave' is home. *Displacement & Migration News*. <https://humanglemedia.com/inside-benue-idp-camp-where-mosquito-net-cave-is-home/>
- Owoaje, E. T., Uchendu, O. C., Ajayi, T. O., & Cadmus, E. O. (2016). A review of the health Problems of the internally displaced persons in Africa. *Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 23(4), 161.
- Rajbhandari, A. K., Dhaubanjari, R., B, K., & Dahal, M. (2018). Knowledge and practice of personal hygiene among secondary school students of grade nine and ten. *Journal of Patan Academy of Health Sciences*, 5(2), 107-113

Taber, K. S. (2018). The use of cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*, 48(6), 1273-1296. doi:10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2

Ukase, P. I., & Jato, T. P. (2022). Socio-economic consequences of conflict: the predicament of internally displaced persons in Benue State. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 5(5), 10-26.